

A Proof of a Polynomial Property

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This paper proves that for a polynomial f with $\deg f \leq n - 1$ and a strictly monotonically decreasing sequence $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^n$, if f satisfies $f(x_i) \leq 0$ when $2 \mid i$ and $f(x_i) \geq 0$ when $2 \nmid i$, then $f(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

Remark: $[n] = [1, n] \cap \mathbb{Z}$.

Proof: Let A, B, C be three distinct elements. We have the following conclusions.

1 Conclusion 1

Let $S_1 = \{S(k, 1)\}_{k \in [t_1]} = (CBCACBCA \cdots)_{k \in [t_1]}$, which satisfied that when $2 \nmid k$ and $k \in [t_1]$, then $S(k, 1) = C$; when $2 \mid k$, $4 \nmid k$ and $k \in [t_1]$, then $S(k, 1) = B$; when $4 \mid k$ and $k \in [t_1]$, then $S(k, 1) = A$. Let $D_1 = \{k(i, 1)\}_{i \in [t_2]}$ be a strictly increasing sequence of positive integers, which satisfied that when $2 \nmid i$ and $i \in [t_2]$, then $S(k(i, 1), 1) \in \{B, C\}$; when $2 \mid i$ and $i \in [t_2]$, then $S(k(i, 1), 1) \in \{A, C\}$. Then $t_2 \leq (\text{The number of } C \text{ in } S_1) + 1$.

The proof of conclusion 1: Let proposition $W_1(i)$ be $k(i, 1) \geq 2i - 1$; then $W_1(1)$ holds. If $W_1(i_0)$ holds ($i_0 \in [t_2 - 1]$), i.e., $k(i_0, 1) \geq 2i_0 - 1$; suppose that $W_1(i_0 + 1)$ does not hold, i.e., $k(i_0 + 1, 1) < 2i_0 + 1$; then $k(i_0 + 1, 1) = 2i_0$. If $2 \mid i_0$, then $A = S(2i_0, 1) = S(k(i_0 + 1, 1), 1) \in \{B, C\}$. contradiction. If $2 \nmid i_0$, then $B = S(2i_0, 1) = S(k(i_0 + 1, 1), 1) \in \{A, C\}$. contradiction. Therefore, $W_1(i_0 + 1)$ holds.

From the inductive principle, it follows that for any $i \in [t_2]$, $W_1(i)$ holds, i.e., $k(i, 1) \geq 2i - 1$, Thus $t_2 \leq \lfloor \frac{t_1 + 1}{2} \rfloor \leq (\text{The number of } C \text{ in } S_1) + 1$.

2 Conclusion 2

Let $S_2 = \{S(k, 2)\}_{k \in [t_3]} = (CACBCACB \cdots)_{k \in [t_3]}$, which satisfied that when $2 \nmid k$ and $k \in [t_3]$, then $S(k, 2) = C$; when $2 \mid k$, $4 \nmid k$ and $k \in [t_3]$, then $S(k, 2) = A$; when $4 \mid k$ and $k \in [t_3]$, then $S(k, 2) = B$. Let $D_2 = \{k(i, 2)\}_{i \in [t_4]}$ be a strictly increasing sequence of positive integers, which satisfied that when $2 \nmid i$ and $i \in [t_4]$, then $S(k(i, 2), 2) \in \{B, C\}$; when $2 \mid i$ and $i \in [t_4]$, then $S(k(i, 2), 2) \in \{A, C\}$. Then $t_4 \leq (\text{The number of } C \text{ in } S_2) + 1$.

The proof of conclusion 2: Let proposition $W_2(i)$ be $k(i, 2) \geq 2i - 3$; then $W_2(1), W_2(2), W_2(3)$ hold.

When $t_4 \geq 4$, if $W_2(i_0)$ holds ($3 \leq i_0 \leq t_4 - 1$), i.e., $k(i_0, 2) \geq 2i_0 - 3$; suppose that $W_2(i_0 + 1)$ does not hold, i.e., $k(i_0 + 1, 2) < 2i_0 - 1$; then $k(i_0 + 1, 2) = 2i_0 - 2$. If $2 \mid i_0$, then $A = S(2i_0 - 2, 2) = S(k(i_0 + 1, 2), 2) \in \{B, C\}$. contradiction. If $2 \nmid i_0$, then $B = S(2i_0 - 2, 2) = S(k(i_0 + 1, 2), 2) \in \{A, C\}$. contradiction. Therefore, $W_2(i_0 + 1)$ holds.

From the inductive principle, it follows that for any $i \in [t_4]$, $W_2(i)$ holds, i.e., $k(i, 2) \geq 2i - 3$, Thus $t_4 \leq \lfloor \frac{t_3 + 3}{2} \rfloor \leq (\text{The number of } C \text{ in } S_1) + 1$.

3 Conclusion 3

Let $S_3 = \{S(k, 3)\}_{k \in [t_5]} = (BCACBCAC \cdots)_{k \in [t_5]}$, which satisfied that when $2 \mid k$ and $k \in [t_5]$, then $S(k, 3) = C$; when $k \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and $k \in [t_5]$, then $S(k, 3) = B$; when $k \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ and $k \in [t_5]$, then $S(k, 3) = A$. Let $D_3 = \{k(i, 3)\}_{i \in [t_6]}$ be a strictly increasing sequence of positive integers, which satisfied that when $2 \nmid i$ and $i \in [t_6]$, then $S(k(i, 3), 3) \in \{B, C\}$; when $2 \mid i$ and $i \in [t_6]$, then $S(k(i, 3), 3) \in \{A, C\}$. Then $t_6 \leq (\text{The number of } C \text{ in } S_1) + 1$.

The proof of conclusion 3: Let proposition $W_3(i)$ be $k(i, 3) \geq 2i - 2$; then $W_3(1)$ holds. If $W_3(i_0)$ holds ($2 \leq i_0 \leq t_6 - 1$), i.e., $k(i_0, 3) \geq 2i_0 - 2$; suppose that $W_3(i_0 + 1)$ does not hold, i.e., $k(i_0 + 1, 3) < 2i_0$; then $k(i_0 + 1, 3) = 2i_0 - 1$. If $2 \mid i_0$, then

$A = S(2i_0 - 1, 1) = S(k(i_0 + 1, 1), 1) \in \{B, C\}$. contradiction. If $2 \nmid i_0$, then $B = S(2i_0 - 1, 1) = S(k(i_0 + 1, 1), 1) \in \{A, C\}$. contradiction. Therefore, $W_1(i_0 + 1)$ holds.

From the inductive principle, it follows that for any $i \in [t_2]$, $W_3(i)$ holds, i.e., $k(i, 3) \geq 2i - 2$, Thus $t_3 \leq \lfloor \frac{t_2 + 2}{2} \rfloor \leq$ (The number of C in S_3)+1.

4 Conclusion 4

An n -term letter sequence $(x_i)_{i \in [n]}$ satisfies either the first set of conditions:

$$\begin{cases} x_i \in \{A, B\} & \text{if } i \in [n] \text{ and } 2 \mid i \text{ (i.e., } i \text{ is even)} \\ x_i = C & \text{if } i \in [n] \text{ and } 2 \nmid i \text{ (i.e., } i \text{ is odd)} \end{cases}$$

or the second set of conditions:

$$\begin{cases} x_i = C & \text{if } i \in [n] \text{ and } 2 \mid i \text{ (i.e., } i \text{ is even)} \\ x_i \in \{A, B\} & \text{if } i \in [n] \text{ and } 2 \nmid i \text{ (i.e., } i \text{ is odd)} \end{cases}$$

and simultaneously satisfies $x_1 \in \{B, C\}$.

For all positive integers i satisfying $2 \leq i \leq n$, define

$$V(i, (x_i)_{i \in [n]}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x_i \in \{A, B\} \\ 2, & \text{if } (x_{i-1}, x_i, x_{i+1}) \in \{(B, C, B), (A, C, A)\} \\ 1, & \text{if } (x_{i-1}, x_i, x_{i+1}) \in \{(B, C, A), (A, C, B)\} \end{cases}$$

Moreover, define

$$V(1, (x_i)_{i \in [n]}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x_1 \in \{A, B\} \\ 1, & \text{if } x_1 = C \end{cases}$$

and

$$V(n, (x_i)_{i \in [n]}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x_n \in \{A, B\} \\ 1, & \text{if } x_n = C \end{cases}$$

Given an m - term strictly increasing sequence of positive integers $\{k_i\}_{i \in [m]}$ that satisfies: for all $i \in [m]$, if $2 \nmid i$, then $x_{k_i} \in \{B, C\}$; and if $2 \mid i$, then $x_{k_i} \in \{A, C\}$. Then it holds that

$$m \leq \sum_{i=1}^n V(i, (x_i)_{i \in [n]}) + 1$$

The proof of conclusion 4: Define $d((x_i)_{i \in [n]})$ as the number of integers i that satisfy $(x_{i-1}, x_i, x_{i+1}) \in \{(B, C, B), (A, C, A)\}$. By Conclusions 1, 2, and 3, when $d((x_i)_{i \in [n]}) = 0$, we have

$$m \leq \sum_{i=1}^n V(i, (x_i)_{i \in [n]}) + 1$$

Suppose that when $d((x_i)_{i \in [n]}) = m_0$ (where $m_0 \in \mathbb{N}$), the inequality $m \leq \sum_{i=1}^n V(i, (x_i)_{i \in [n]}) + 1$ holds. We next prove that when $d((x_i)_{i \in [n]}) = m_0 + 1$, the same inequality still holds.

Given $d((x_i)_{i \in [n]}) = m_0 + 1$:

If there exists i_0 such that $(x_{i_0-1}, x_{i_0}, x_{i_0+1}) = (B, C, B)$, consider the sequence:

$$x'_i = \begin{cases} x_i, & 1 \leq i \leq i_0 \\ A, & i = i_0 + 1 \\ x_{i-2}, & i_0 + 2 \leq i \leq n + 2 \end{cases}$$

Conversely, if there exists i_0 such that $(x_{i_0-1}, x_{i_0}, x_{i_0+1}) = (A, C, A)$, consider:

$$x'_i = \begin{cases} x_i, & 1 \leq i \leq i_0 \\ B, & i = i_0 + 1 \\ x_{i-2}, & i_0 + 2 \leq i \leq n + 2 \end{cases}$$

For such x'_i , we have:

$$d((x'_i)_{i \in [n+2]}) = d((x_i)_{i \in [n]}) - 1 = m_0,$$

and

$$\sum_{i=1}^n V(i, (x_i)_{i \in [n]}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n+2} V(i, (x'_i)_{i \in [n+2]}).$$

Note that $x'_{i_0-1} = x_{i_0-1} \in \{A, B\}$ and $x'_{i_0+1} \in \{A, B\}$. Since $i-2$ and i have the same parity, and i_0+1 and i_0-1 have the same parity, the sequence $(x'_i)_{i \in [n+2]}$ satisfies either:

$$\begin{cases} x'_i \in \{A, B\} & \text{if } 2 \mid i \text{ and } i \in [n+2], \\ x'_i = C & \text{if } 2 \nmid i \text{ and } i \in [n+2] \end{cases}$$

or:

$$\begin{cases} x'_i = C & \text{if } 2 \mid i \text{ and } i \in [n+2], \\ x'_i \in \{A, B\} & \text{if } 2 \nmid i \text{ and } i \in [n+2] \end{cases}$$

Moreover, $x'_1 = x_1 \in \{B, C\}$. By the induction hypothesis (since $d((x'_i)_{i \in [n+2]}) = m_0$), we have:

$$m \leq \sum_{i=1}^{n+2} V(i, (x'_i)_{i \in [n+2]}) + 1 = \sum_{i=1}^n V(i, (x_i)_{i \in [n]}) + 1.$$

Thus, the conclusion holds when $d((x_i)_{i \in [n]}) = m_0 + 1$. From the inductive principle, Conclusion 4 holds for all cases.

5 Conclusion 5

Given a polynomial $f(x)$ satisfying $\deg f \leq n-1$, let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^n$ be a strictly decreasing sequence of real numbers. For all integers i with $0 \leq i \leq n$: if $2 \mid i$, then $f(x_i) \leq 0$; if $2 \nmid i$, then $f(x_i) \geq 0$. Then it holds that $f(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

The proof of conclusion 5: For number sets K_1 and K_2 , we say K_1 is greater than K_2 if and only if every number in K_1 is greater than every number in K_2 .

Suppose $f(x)$ is not identically zero. Let $\{y_i\}_{i=1}^{m_1}$ denote all zeros of $f(x)$, and define $y'_i = \{y_i\}$ (each y'_i is a singleton set). Let $I = [x_n, x_0] \setminus (\bigcup_{i=1}^{m_1} y'_i)$.

Then I is a union of finitely many pairwise disjoint open intervals or half-open/half-closed intervals. On each such interval, $f(x)$ is non-zero and either always positive or always negative. Moreover, when these intervals and all y'_i ($i \in [m_1]$) are ordered in strictly decreasing order as $\{z_i\}_{i=1}^{m_2}$ (where each z_i is a set of numbers), intervals and singleton sets alternate.

Define the function $g(i)$ as:

$$g(i) = \begin{cases} A, & \text{if } f > 0 \text{ on } z_i, \\ B, & \text{if } f < 0 \text{ on } z_i, \\ C, & \text{if } f = 0 \text{ on } z_i. \end{cases}$$

Note that the sequence $\{g(i)\}_{i \in [m_2]}$ satisfies either

$$\begin{cases} g(i) \in \{A, B\} & \text{if } 2 \mid i \text{ and } i \in [m_2], \\ g(i) = C & \text{if } 2 \nmid i \text{ and } i \in [m_2] \end{cases}$$

or

$$\begin{cases} g(i) = C & \text{if } 2 \mid i \text{ and } i \in [m_2], \\ g(i) \in \{A, B\} & \text{if } 2 \nmid i \text{ and } i \in [m_2] \end{cases}$$

Let k_i satisfy $x_{i-1} \in z_{k_i}$ for $i \in [n+1]$. Suppose $k_{i_1} = k_{i_1+1}$; let $k_{i_1} = j$. Then $x_{i_1}, x_{i_1-1} \in z_j$. Since one of $f(x_{i_1})$ and $f(x_{i_1-1})$ is ≥ 0 and the other is ≤ 0 , both must be 0. Thus, x_{i_1} is a zero of $f(x)$, so z_j is a singleton, a contradiction. Since both $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^n$ and $\{z_i\}_{i=1}^{m_2}$ are strictly monotonic decreasing, $\{k_i\}_{i \in [n+1]}$ is strictly monotonic increasing.

For odd i , $f(x_{i-1}) \leq 0$, so $g(z_{k_i}) \in \{B, C\}$; for even i , $f(x_{i-1}) \geq 0$, so $g(z_{k_i}) \in \{A, C\}$. The sequence $\{k_i\}_{i=1}^{n+1}$ has $n+1$ terms.

By Conclusion 4:

$$n+1 \leq \sum_{i=1}^n V(i, (g(i))_{i \in [m_2]}) + 1$$

According to the fact that sign-preserving zeros must be multiple roots, it follows that

$$\text{Number of roots of } f(x) \geq \sum_{i=1}^n V(i, (g(i))_{i \in [m_2]})$$

Thus, $n \leq \text{Number of roots of } f(x)$, contradicting $\deg f \leq n - 1$ (a polynomial of degree $\leq n - 1$ has at most $n - 1$ roots). Hence, the initial assumption is false, so $f(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

6 Conclusion 6

We have the following conclusions.

6.1 Conclusion 6.1

Let $f(x)$ be a polynomial with $\deg f \leq n - 1$, and let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^n$ be a strictly decreasing sequence of real numbers. If $2 \mid i$ (i.e., i is even) and $i \in [n]$, then $f(x_i) \leq 0$; if $2 \nmid i$ (i.e., i is odd) and $i \in [n]$, then $f(x_i) \geq 0$. Then $f(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

6.2 Conclusion 6.2

Let $f(x)$ be a polynomial with $\deg f \leq n - 1$, and let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^n$ be a strictly decreasing sequence of real numbers. If $2 \mid i$ (i.e., i is even) and $i \in [n]$, then $f(x_i) \geq 0$; if $2 \nmid i$ (i.e., i is odd) and $i \in [n]$, then $f(x_i) \leq 0$. Then $f(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

Proof of Conclusion 6.2: Let $h_1(x) = -f(x)$. By Conclusion 6.1, the result follows.

6.3 Conclusion 6.3

Let $f(x)$ be a polynomial with $\deg f \leq n - 1$, and let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^n$ be a strictly increasing sequence of real numbers. If $2 \mid i$ (i.e., i is even) and $i \in [n]$, then $f(x_i) \leq 0$; if $2 \nmid i$ (i.e., i is odd) and $i \in [n]$, then $f(x_i) \geq 0$. Then $f(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

Proof of Conclusion 6.3: Let $h_2(x) = f(-x)$ and $y_i = -x_i$. By Conclusion 6.1, the result follows.

6.4 Conclusion 6.4

Let $f(x)$ be a polynomial with $\deg f \leq n - 1$, and let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^n$ be a strictly increasing sequence of real numbers. If $2 \mid i$ (i.e., i is even) and $i \in [n]$, then $f(x_i) \geq 0$; if $2 \nmid i$ (i.e., i is odd) and $i \in [n]$, then $f(x_i) \leq 0$. Then $f(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

Proof of Conclusion 6.4: Let $h_3(x) = f(-x)$ and $r_i = -x_i$. By Conclusion 6.2, the result follows.

7 Research Background

Initially, I investigated the following problem: Given $f(x) = 2^{n-1}x^n + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} a_i x^i$, prove that $\max_{-1 \leq x \leq 1} |f(x)| \geq 1$ holds for all cases, and identify all $f(x)$ such that $\max_{-1 \leq x \leq 1} |f(x)| = 1$. I first noticed that Chebyshev polynomials satisfy this conclusion and provided the following proof:

Consider $g(x) = f(x) - T_n(x)$; then $\deg g(x) \leq n - 1$. Suppose $|f(x)| < 1$ holds for all $x \in [-1, 1]$; then $-1 < g(x) + T_n(x) < 1$ holds for all $x \in [-1, 1]$, which is equivalent to $-1 - T_n(x) < g(x) < 1 - T_n(x)$ holding for all $x \in [-1, 1]$. Consider $x_k = \cos \frac{k\pi}{n}$; then $-1 - T_n(x_k) < g(x_k) < 1 - T_n(x_k)$ holds for all $1 \leq k \leq n$.

Since $T_n(x_k) = 1$ when k is even (i.e., $2 \mid k$), and $T_n(x_k) = -1$ when k is odd (i.e., $2 \nmid k$), we have: - When $2 \mid k$, $g(x_k) < 0$; - When $2 \nmid k$, $g(x_k) > 0$.

Thus, for any $k \in [n]$, $g(x)$ has a zero in the interval $\left(\cos \frac{(k-1)\pi}{n}, \cos \frac{k\pi}{n}\right)$, meaning $g(x)$ has at least n zeros. Note that $g(x)$ is not a constant function and $\deg g(x) \leq n - 1$, which leads to a contradiction. Therefore, $\max_{-1 \leq x \leq 1} |f(x)| \geq 1$ holds for all cases.

Lemma: Given a polynomial $h(x)$ satisfying $\deg h(x) \leq n - 1$, and $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^n$ being a strictly decreasing sequence of real numbers. If $h(x_i) \leq 0$ when i is even (i.e., $2 \mid i$) and $0 \leq i \leq n$, and $h(x_i) \geq 0$ when i is odd (i.e., $2 \nmid i$) and $0 \leq i \leq n$, then $h(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

The proof of this lemma can be found in this paper.

Suppose $|f(x)| \leq 1$ holds for all $x \in [-1, 1]$; then: When $2 \mid k$, $f(x_k) \leq 1 = T_n(x_k)$; When $2 \nmid k$, $f(x_k) \geq -1 = T_n(x_k)$.

Therefore, $g(x_k) \leq 0$ when $2 \mid k$, and $g(x_k) \geq 0$ when $2 \nmid k$. Note that $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^n$ is a strictly decreasing sequence of real numbers; according to the above lemma, $g(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$, so $f(x) = T_n(x)$.

Since $T_n(x) = \cos(n \arccos x) \leq 1$ for all $x \in [-1, 1]$, it follows that $\max_{-1 \leq x \leq 1} f(x) = 1$ if and only if $f(x) = T_n(x)$. The conclusion of this paper serves as a lemma in the proof of the aforementioned result.

8 References and Acknowledgments

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